

GENERAL TYPOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF LYRIC CYCLES

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Abstract. *In this article, the issue of general typological features of the poetic cycle is studied, as well as the study of this topic abroad, in particular, in Russian literary studies, is examined in detail. The article also talks about the artistic features of the cycle, the structure of artistic works, the system of aesthetic tools used in the composition of the cycle, and it is emphasized that it is important to study the relationship between the artistic idea and the content of the work.*

Keywords: *artistic idea, cycle, compositional integrity, character of experience, single subject, system of aesthetic means, artistic thinking, imagery, perfection of series.*

ОБЩАЯ ТИПОЛОГИЧЕСКАЯ ХАРАКТЕРИСТИКА ЛИРИЧЕСКИХ ЦИКЛОВ

Аннотация. *В данной статье исследуется вопрос об общих типологических особенностях поэтического цикла, а также подробно рассматривается изучение данной темы за рубежом, в частности, в русском литературоведении. В статье также говорится о художественных особенностях цикла, структуре художественных произведений, системе эстетических средств, используемых в композиции цикла, и подчеркивается важность изучения взаимосвязи между художественной идеей и содержанием работы.*

Ключевые слова: *художественная мысль, цикл, композиционная целостность, характер переживания, единичный предмет, система эстетических средств, художественное мышление, образность, совершенство серии.*

INTRODUCTION

In Uzbek literature, there are many examples of artistic and aesthetic research of cyclicity. It is known that a holistic artistic-aesthetic concept integrates cyclicity into one system.

Literary scholars comment on the formation process of cyclicity in Uzbek literature by emphasizing that the roots of this form come from the literature of ancient times. This idea has soul. Because the ancient stone inscriptions have aspects such as gradualism and consistency according to their specific characteristics, and such content is visible in the construction of poems and descriptions of experiences. The statement that the quatrains contained in the work "Devoni lug'otit turk" are subordinated to a single idea and within the framework of one topic, the main aspect of which is interpreted based on the relationship between man and nature, and the common aspect serves as the basis for their main content. data indicate that the cycle was formed in ancient and medieval times. Generality, consistency and cyclicity around the main theme are created on the basis of lyrical laws.

While several poems within the same theme form a cycle, it is also observed that in addition to common typological features, there must be a common idea, independent experience features. In this sense, Oybek's "Chimyon cycle", Mirtemir's "Korakalpoq notebook" cycle, Erkin Vahidov's "Wise village anecdotes" cycle are recognized as perfect examples of experience

It can be said that the main purpose of writing a cycle of poems is to describe the process of evolution in the human psyche, to demonstrate once again what the human being in the

material world is capable of by reflecting the very complex and dialectical aspects of the concept of humanity.

One of the unique aspects of poetic cycles is the general idea that unites the poems in the cycle in terms of content and logic.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The ideational tendency is of particular importance in the phenomenon of cyclicity as an aspect characteristic of every artistic work. In cycle poems, the artistic idea is like a pillar that unites the poems in it. In particular, Erkin Vahidov's cycle "Poems of the Caucasus" has such characteristics. The poems in this series are united by the idea of describing the impressions of the young poet who traveled to the Caucasus. Ideology in the cycle The poem "Sail" with the description of a white sailboat sailing in Baku Bay, the poem "To the peak of Ararat" with the lyrical hero's appeal to the high mountain peak reaching the clouds, " The poem "Azganush" expresses the heart of a young poet who is in love with a beautiful Armenian girl. It is possible to witness that the poem "Farewell" is reflected by the description of the farewell moments of the poet, who is a lyrical hero, with the land of the Caucasus.

RESULTS

The Uzbek poet, who is the lyrical hero of the poems in the cycle, could not hide his admiration for the scenery of another charming country, he also devoted a place to the description of the beauties of this country, he entertained them as a young man in love, and during a short-term trip Such as the fact that he did not even have time to express himself to him in the poem embodies the main reality that serves the main idea of this poem.

Another cycle of Erkin Vahidov is "Canadian cycle", which includes the poet's poems such as "Twelve O'Clock in Calgary", "Auction", "The Lion Trainer", "Woman on the Street". It is clear from the content of these poems that the main idea is to describe the impressions of the lyric hero's trip to Canada.

The poet's poem "Auction" talks about the reality of the market, which is a form of wholesale trade. Aspects such as the hustle and bustle, the enjoyment of every moment for businessmen are shown separately.

E.Vahidov's famous poem "The lion trainer" is also from this series, and it was published with the comment "Vancouver audience". The main idea of the poem is the concept of will, which is one of the eternal problems of mankind. succeeds in revealing the sad reality of life in both. The poet effectively uses the art of speech to realize the ideological goal of the poem. Regarding the one who advocates jumping from the ring of fire with a whip:

- Weak man!!

So don't whip me!

... Go!

I will not jump from the fire!

Don't bother!

Do you know –

Who am I and who are you, poor thing! [1, 293]

threatening with horrible words such as, and the person's response to it leads to the solution of the problem:

understand my situation

Don't rebel brother

Both of us in front of the wheel
Exactly the same.
Although I play the lion
Although I am Adam,
I expect sugar at the end of the month
I am from my master [1, 293].

That is, the lion trainer is also powerless in front of his master, he is also a slave who waits for "sugar" - his salary - for his children and livelihood. The poem also expects the lion, who is its master, to eat from the teacher, without whom it will surely perish. The need for both of them to obey someone in order to live, to serve their own food is a common aspect in them, and this fact of life shakes even a majestic animal like a lion:

- That's it, stop!
Don't make my heart bleed, man!
Let this wheel fire
Risk day!..
Lion fire belt
He shot himself [1, 294].

It seems that the lion realizes that the concept of Erk, which is a simple fact of life, does not stand in the way of the problem of livelihood and food. People get angry when they hand over their freedom to owners, chiefs, and masters.

The poet's poem "The ship of Alisher Navoi" reflects the poet's surprise when he saw Alisher Navoi's ship, where the poet Bahri was wandering around.

The great Alisher is awake until death
Wandering in the ocean of the world [1, 295].

It can be said that recognition of Navoi's genius from poetry is eternal, and that Navoi's spirit travels around the world, and his memory is always in hearts, and this genius creator will never be forgotten.

The lyrical characters of the two poems in this cycle are poetic characters themselves. The visionary aspect of the poem is similar. That is, whoever are the poetic images reflected in them, through their speech, the poet aims to draw attention to the negative aspects of the depicted country. One of them is the person lying on the side of the street, forgotten by people, in the poem "Song of Forgetting", and the other is the description of the light-hearted woman in the poem "Woman on the Side of the Street". Even though both of them are at the level of social waste in their living environment, the poet shows the attitude towards the concept of humanism in that society by speaking from their language and conveying that they are also human beings, that they have the right to live, and that their situation is due to desperation. In the poem "Song of Oblivion":

I'm lying on the side of the road
There is no one to ask what happened.
I do not exist for the world,
Such a world does not exist for me [1, 296].

by saying that a person who has become alienated from the world he lives in forgets this world, that is, disobeys the laws and moral norms of society, falls into a careless and arrogant dream, forgets his own identity, and acts unwillingly made

The same woman, who is also a lyrical hero in the poem "The Woman on the Street", calls the ugly society she lives in a "free country" and says that her "profession" is legal and no one has the right to restrict her. 'by the teeth, Fakhsh and Fujur are accepted as the norm in this society.

In general, the poems of the Canadian cycle reflect the various impressions of the trip to this country, but the poems of the cycle do not describe the speech of a single lyrical hero, but also use the speech of poetic images, which is based on the main idea and purpose of the poet's poems on this topic. can reach

DISCUSSION

In the works of the sonnet genre, the composition and the proportion of the arrangement of the plot elements justify the cycle. Regardless of the number of sonnets, there is a common compositional structure that binds them together. It is also possible to notice the conditional arrangement of plot elements corresponding to this. That is, sonnets serve as a description of the experiences of the lyrical hero and an element according to the proposed idea. Each cycle has its own lyrical hero. And in the center is the process of evolution in the psyche of this lyrical hero and its consequences.

The sonnet cycles written by Rauf Parfi and Fakhriyor are worth evaluating as a great achievement of Uzbek sonnet writing due to their high content and artistry. Hamid Mirzaev dwells on the cycle of sonnets in the poetry of Rauf Parfi, and emphasizes that the philosophical spirit is the leader in them, and includes most of the poet's sonnet collections such as "Sunbula", "Barnobonu", "Pain", "Michelangelo's love" in the cycles. introduces. One of the unique aspects of cycles is that compositional integrity applies to both form and content. Rauf Parfi's collections such as "Without You", "Longing for God", "Black Wall", "Thakur's Last Poem", "Passenger", "Hamlet", "A Letter to My Mother in the World" can also be called sonnet cycle examples. . The poet's cycle "Without You" includes three sonnets.

The unique feature of the sonnet cycles created by Rauf Parfi is that the elements of compositional integrity present in each sonnet are also characteristic of the cycle. That is, in the first sonnet there is a description of the proposed problem in the idea, in the second sonnet there is a development of the experience, and in the third sonnet there is a solution and a lock. The peculiarity of the sonnet cycles created by Rauf Parfi is that the elements of compositional unity present in each sonnet are also characteristic of the cycle. That is, the description of the problem in the first sonnet, the development of the experience in the second sonnet, and the solution and closure in the third sonnet. given In the "Without You" cycle, the feeling that is unknown except for the compositional elements in the first sonnet is revealed to be "love" in the end of the sonnet. It can be said that the problem in the sonnet, that is, the love heart, which is the central lyrical hero, suffers from lack of love. In the second sonnet, according to the development of the experience, it is described that love is revived, it is brought to the sea by a ship, flowers and birds in nature, as if they sensed an unpleasant situation, are in a hadic state, and they handcuff the heart in love with the "love" that fell from the ship in order not to get close to it. In the third sonnet, there is an invitation to wake up "love", whose soul is dying, and to accompany the lover in his sufferings and pains. According to the content of the sonnet, love is an eternal feeling, and the real person is a transitory, temporary nature, and the lyrical hero expresses his desire not to lose the happiness of enjoying this divine feeling for this short time.

The opportunity is passing. Time is eternal,

Saving is a saving person in the world -
There is a language of conscience, and its love is faith -
This time invites native people [5, 90].

Abdulla Sher, one of the Uzbek sonnet writers, has unique cycles under the name "Pronoun of Love" containing eleven sonnets each named "Men", "Sen", "U", "Biz". In Mirpolat Mirzo's work, there is also a sonnet cycle consisting of twenty-eight sonnets, and these cycles were formed according to all the characteristics.

While Abdulla Sher's sonnets reflect the sorrow of love and the sufferings of emigration, the sonnets of Mirpolat Mirza's cycle "Mother" do not express the above interpretations of love typical of traditional sonnets, but worship the figure of the mother, who has a unique social meaning. An example of a sonnet on this topic is also found in the poetry of Rauf Parfi, and this cycle is called "A letter to the world to my mother". The cycle consists of three sonnets, and these sonnets are based on the main idea, which serves as the nucleus. "explained. That is, the great love and value of the mother is described. The common goal is the core of the "Mother" cycle. In this cycle, the sonnets are also subordinated to a single goal. From its content, a high respect for the Mother, who is a noble character, can be observed.

One of the unique aspects of cycles is that the compositional integrity applies to both form and content. In M. Mirza's "Mother" cycle, the same compositional unity is expressed through the idea of explaining the description of children's experiences. In this cycle of sonnets, the poems individually meet the specific requirements of the sonnet in their own way. There are also expressive absurdities with I. In particular, there are places in the sonnets where the description of the author's family environment prevails over the experiences of the lyrical hero. Taking into account that poetry cannot be separated from the poet's personality, formal researches of this specific cycle We have reason to believe that it is a successful experience.

Sonnets call the reader to fight, look to the future with hope, it seems that the sad, sad, tragic image of human love ensures the longevity of the cycle of sonnets. The essence of the cycles is that the poet's experiences can be described in a consistent and unique sequence, and the author's thoughts and themes are described in a resonant way. The cycle "Onajon" is a work worthy of evaluation as one of the successful works dedicated to mothers.

"The lyrical cycle allows the poet to express a holistic understanding of reality, a holistic view of the world and a person, while preserving the characteristics of lyricism" [3, 65]. Cyclicism in Uzbek sonnet writing is a phenomenon that has already formed both according to its artistic and aesthetic characteristics and based on its theoretical basis. Specific typological characteristics of sonnet cycles have been formed. These include features such as the fact that the sonnets in the cycle are combined from three to ten sonnets, they are described in an essentially consistent and sequential relationship, they complement each other in terms of content and lead to a conclusion.

CONCLUSIONS

It can be said that in the created poetic cycles, the reality is reflected as a whole, subordinated to the main idea. The integrity of man and being is also reflected in the relationship of the lyrical heroes of the poems to the environment in which they move. The existence of unity in such aspects as the main idea and theme of the cycle, characteristic images, subjective organization of the text, intertextual relations, composition, subject dynamics and chronotope can be a clear proof that it is a cycle.

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